

EVALUATION OF THE WETTABILITY OF ALUMINUM ALLOYS WITH SiC PARTICULATES BY MEANS OF PRESSURE INFILTRATION

A. Alonso^a, A. Pamies^a, J. Narciso^a, C. Garcia-Cordovilla^a, and E. Louis^{a,b}

a. Industria Española del Aluminio, Centro de Investigación y Desarrollo, Apartado 25, E-03080 Alicante, Spain.

b. Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidad de Alicante, Apartado 99, E-03080 Alicante, Spain.

ABSTRACT

The wettability at metal/ceramic particulates interfaces has been evaluated by means of an infiltration technique that permits a determination of the threshold pressure and of the infiltration kinetics. The work was carried out on pure aluminum, an Al-Pb alloy and several binary and ternary alloys of the Al-Si-Mg system. The commercial alloys A-356, A-357 and AA6061 were also considered. Two types of SiC particulates of average diameters 51 μm and 27 μm , respectively, were used. All infiltrations were carried out in air. The results indicate that the changes in the threshold pressure promoted by alloying are essentially due to the corresponding changes in the surface tension of aluminum. The effects of wetting seem to be less important, as expected for oxidized aluminum.

Keywords: wettability, aluminum alloys, silicon carbide, composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

The interest in the development of manufacturing processes of Metal Matrix Composites (MMC) has been steadily increasing in recent years [1]. The most important limitation to the fabrication of MMC by liquid-phase processes is the compatibility between the reinforcement and the matrix. This compatibility is particularly important in the case of aluminum based composites, because Al is usually covered with a thin oxide layer that prevents wetting [2], and, when uncovered, it readily reacts with most ceramics. Wettability and reactivity determine the quality of the bond between both materials, and, therefore, the final properties

of the composite.

Wettability is usually evaluated by measuring the contact angle between the liquid and the solid [3]. If the ceramic is in the form of particulates or whiskers, this measurement is, however, not possible. In this case, wettability can be studied by means of infiltration of the liquid through packed samples of the particulate [4-8]. As discussed below, this method permits a measurement of the threshold pressure and to study the kinetics of infiltration [4].

Spontaneous infiltration of a liquid into a porous media takes place when the liquid wets the solid. Otherwise, a minimum external pressure should be applied. This threshold pressure P_0 is related to the contact angle θ and the particle size through the so-called capillary law [4]

$$P_0 = 6\lambda \gamma_{lv} \cos\theta \frac{V_p}{(1-V_p)D} \quad (1)$$

where γ_{lv} is the liquid-vapour surface tension and λ a factor which depends on the geometry of the particulates. D and V_p are the mean diameter and volume fraction of the particulate, respectively. In order to obtain information on wetting at the interface through the measurement of the threshold pressure, the geometrical factor λ in Eq. (1) has to be determined in advance [7].

The flow of an incompressible fluid through a porous media is governed by Darcy's law [4]. For unidirectional flow, and neglecting any effect of gravity, Darcy's law can be written as

$$h = \left[\frac{2 k t \Delta P}{\mu (1-V_p)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where ΔP is the pressure drop in the liquid metal given by the difference between the total pressure drop, that can be identified with the applied pressure P , and the threshold pressure P_0 , namely, $\Delta P = P - P_0$.

The infiltration experiment consists in forcing the liquid metal to infiltrate samples of packed particulates by applying pressure by means of a pressurized gas. The pressure is raised as fast as possible up to a chosen value, kept constant for a period of time and then reduced down to atmospheric pressure. Thus, the infiltrated height is measured as a function of applied pressure. This allows a determination of the threshold pressure. On the other hand the infiltration kinetics can be studied by measuring the infiltrated height as a function of time at a pressure above threshold. In a previous publication we have shown that the results obtained by means of this technique follow, capillary and Darcy's laws (Eqs. (1) and (2)).

In this work we have used this method to evaluate the wettability between SiC particulates and several laboratory and commercial aluminum alloys. The measurements were carried out by means of an experimental set up designed and assembled in our laboratory [6,7]. All experiments were carried out in air, thus liquid aluminum is expected to be covered by a thin oxide layer all throughout the infiltrations.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The work was carried out on aluminum of commercial purity (typically higher than 99.98%), an Al-Pb alloy and several binary and ternary alloys of the Al-Si-Mg system prepared in our laboratories. The commercial alloys A356, A357 and AA6061 were also investigated. The composition of these alloys, as determined by means of atomic absorption, are given in Table 1. Two types of SiC particulates black (98.7% purity) and green (99.5% purity) of mean diameters $51\ \mu\text{m}$ and $27\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively, were used. The combinations alloy/particulate used in the experiments are reported in Table 2.

A schematic drawing of the pressure chamber is shown in figure 1. As described in Ref. [7], here we shall only outline its main features. The pressure chamber was made of stainless steel and has 30 cm I.D., 36.4 cm O.D. and 35 cm height, whereas the bottom and the lid are 3.2 cm thick. It can support a maximum pressure of 3000 kPa. A resistance furnace was located inside the chamber. Pressure was measured with a transmitter, and controlled within $\pm 2\ \text{kPa}$. Pressure and temperature were registered during the experiment. All pressures are referred to atmospheric pressure.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of the pressure chamber.

The particulates were packed into quartz tubes of 5 mm I.D. x 20 cm length. At each packing step approximately 0.04 g of particulates were added, there were applied 3 seconds of vibrations to break layering, and the powder was subjected to 20 strokes of a 35 g weight from a constant height (10 cm). The procedure was repeated until the compact reached a height of $\approx 3.5\ \text{cm}$. In order to determine the particle volume fraction V_p , the quartz tube was weighed before and after the powder was packed inside it, and its diameter measured

at five points along its perimeter. Then a measure of the length of the packed powder allowed to obtain V_p . The resultant volume fraction V_p may vary for the different particulates [7] (Table 2). The melt side of the compact was plugged with alumina paper 6% of theoretical density to avoid depacking and skim off the alumina scum during infiltration. A ceramic rod was placed on the top of the preforms to prevent them from moving upwards in the quartz tube during infiltration.

The metal was melted in alumina crucibles of 45 mm internal diameter x 72 mm height. The infiltrations were carried out at a melt temperature of $750^\circ \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The metal surface was cleaned just before the immersion of the quartz tube containing the packed specimens. As no inert gas was introduced into the packed powder, it is expected that, along the whole infiltration process, a thin oxide layer will cover the surface of aluminum. The chamber was closed and the tube held in the melt for 3 minutes. Pressure was then applied with nitrogen gas at a rate of $50\text{-}60 \text{ kPa}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, up to the chosen pressure. After a fixed period of time (120 s in the present work), the chamber was vented at a rate of $30\text{-}70 \text{ kPa}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The sample was taken out of the melt and air cooled, it was sectioned and the infiltration height measured with a precision gauge. In the alloys containing magnesium, a reaction was observed between magnesium and the quartz tube, to produce magnesium oxide and free silicon that increased the silicon content of the melt up to 1.2 wt%.

Table 1. Chemical composition (in wt %) of the commercial alloys investigated in this work, as determined by means of atomic absorption.

Alloy	Mg	Si	Cu	Fe	Ti	Mn
A356	0.32	6.85	0.002	0.23	0.06	0.002
Nominal	0.25-0.45	6.5-7.5	0.2 max	0.2 max	0.2 max	0.1 max
A357	0.62	7.47	0.008	0.21	0.077	0.001
Nominal	0.4-0.7	6.5-7.5	0.2 max	0.2 max	0.2 max	0.1 max
AA-6061	1.05	0.62	0.29	0.34	0.017	0.072
Nominal	0.8-1.2	0.4-0.8	0.15-0.4	0.7 max	0.15 max	0.1 max

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Infiltration results: Darcy's law

The experimental data for the infiltrated height versus applied pressure for two of the alloys of Table 1 are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. To determine the threshold pressure we either fitted

a curve to the data or extrapolated the results to zero penetration. The latter was done when the infiltration height raised very abruptly as a function of pressure. This usually occurs for large particles, although the role of the condition of the particulates surface and of the interface metal/ceramic can be significant. The fitted curve is,

$$P = a h^2 + b \quad (3)$$

where a and b are constants, the latter gives the threshold pressure. The fitted curves and the regression coefficients are also given in figures 2 and 3. The fittings can be considered as reasonably good, indicating that the present results for the infiltrated height versus applied pressure approximately follow Darcy's law. The results for the threshold pressure of the different systems investigated in this work are given in Table 2. Some tests gave very small values for the infiltration height at pressures clearly below threshold, as it is likely that those results are due to depacking of the powder close to the melt [7], they have not been included in the fittings of Eq. (4).

Figure 2. Infiltrated height as a function of applied pressure for alloy A-356 and pure aluminum. SiC particulates of type black. The fitted curve for the alloy is $P = 339 + 5.7 \times 10^{-2} h^2$ ($r = 0.98$).

Figure 3. Infiltrated height as a function of applied pressure for alloy AA-6061 and pure aluminum. SiC particulates of type green. The fitted curve for the alloy is $P = 510 + 6.3 \times 10^{-2} h^2$ ($r = 0.98$).

3.2. Threshold Pressures

In a previous publication [7] we have shown that P_0 decreases as $1/D$, in agreement with the capillary law. The results for the threshold pressure reported in Table 2 show that it also decreases with the surface tension of the alloy [9,10], as indicated by Eq. (1). The surface tension of the binary and ternary alloys of the Al-Si-Mg system shown in Table 2 were

calculated from the data reported in ref. [10], whereas that of the Al-Pb alloy was taken from ref. [7]. In order to quantify this result, we have evaluated which percentage of the change in P_0 is not due to a corresponding change in surface tension, as follows.

For a given particulate and applying the capillary law to pure aluminum and a particular aluminum alloy, we can eliminate the geometric factor λ by writing:

$$\cos\theta_{\text{alloy}} = \frac{\gamma_{\text{Al}}}{\gamma_{\text{alloy}}} \frac{P_0^{\text{alloy}}}{P_0^{\text{Al}}} \cos\theta_{\text{Al}} \quad (4)$$

This equation relates the contact angle for a given aluminum alloy θ_{alloy} with the contact angle of pure aluminum θ_{Al} , and the corresponding threshold pressures and liquid-vapour surface tensions. Note that this equation is only valid for a set of experimental data corresponding to the same particulate, and, therefore, for constant D , V_p , and λ .

In applying Eq. (4) we have taken the contact angle for pure aluminum from ref. [2]. However, we are aware of the fact that the experimental conditions under which it was measured (using the sessile drop method) are not the same than the present conditions. According to Laurent et al. [2] the most adequate contact angle between aluminum and SiC for short time contacts in which the thin oxide film at the aluminum surface is eliminated by mechanical pressure, is $120^\circ \pm 5$. However, this contact angle is strongly time dependent and it was obtained for polished monocrystals of SiC. Impurities and the different roughness of our SiC particulates can alter this angle.

The contact angles calculated from Eq. (4) are reported in Table 2. All angles correspond to non wetting systems ($\theta > 0$). It is noted that the maximum change in θ required to fit all experimental data for P_0^{alloy} is smaller than 10%. This indicates that the changes in the threshold pressure induced by alloying are essentially related to the changes in the surface tension of aluminum. The alloys containing both magnesium and silicon show a significant decrease in the contact angle; this result deserves a more detailed study.

Table 2. Results of the infiltration experiments (at $T= 750^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the alloys of Table 1. γ_{lv} is the surface tension of the liquid metal (mN.m^{-1}). V_p is the particle volume fraction and D their average diameter (μm). P_0 is the threshold pressure (kPa), and θ the contact angle fitted to the experimental data for P_0 , assuming a contact angle for pure aluminum of 120° .

Metal		SiC Particulates			Infiltration	
Alloy	γ_{lv}	Type	D	V_p	P_0	θ
pure Al	863	green	27	0.57	570	120°
Al-4wt% Mg	806	green	27	0.57	520	120°
Al-13wt% Si	833	green	27	0.57	530	120°
Al-13wt% Si- 5wt% Mg	776	green	27	0.57	370	111°
AA6061	836	green	27	0.57	520	118°
pure Al	863	black	51	0.59	405	120°
Al-1wt% Pb	662	black	51	0.59	280	117°
A356	846	black	51	0.59	340	115°
A357	840	black	51	0.59	350	116°

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